

Resistance ratings of varieties in Kerala, India.

Pedigree	Cultures (no.)	Rating score ^a						
		Blast	Bacterial blight	Sheath blight	Helminthosporium	Brown planthoppers	Grassy stunt virus	Rice tungro virus
Triveni/IR1875-78-1-3-1	1	0	2	2	2	—	1	1
Triveni/IR2071-251-1-1	2	0-3	2-3	2-4	0-2	1-2	3	3
IR1702/CH 5	1	1	2	2	0	4	1	1
Jaya/IR1820-210-2	2	0-2	1-2	2-3	2-3	3-4	7	1
12814/SI 26 (Indonesian line)	10	1-3	1-2	0	0	2-4	7	1
Jaya/IR2153-26-3-5-6	1	1	2	2	0	3	7	1
Bharathi/IR2071-625-3-4	11	1-3	2-3	1-3	0	1-2	3	3
Triveni/Mudgo	2	2-3	3-4	2-3	0	1-3	3	3
Triveni/IR2061-464-2-3	3	2-4	2-3	2-3	0	1-2	3	3
Triveni/IR1539	12	2-4	3-4	3-4	0	2	7	3

^aRated on a scale of 0-9: 0 = highly resistant; 9 = highly susceptible.

Brown planthopper symposium

A symposium on the brown planthopper was held during the International Rice Research Conference, 18-22 April 1977.

The symposium included formal papers and planning sessions. Papers on the following topics were presented:

- The Brown Planthopper Problem
- Economic Thresholds, Nature of Damage, and Losses Caused by the Brown Planthopper
- Ecology of the Brown Planthopper in the Tropics
- Ecology of the Brown Planthopper in Temperate Regions
- Brown Planthopper Migration
- Cultural Control of the Brown Planthopper
- Biological Control of the Brown Planthopper
- Factors Governing Susceptibility and Resistance of Certain Rice Varieties to the Brown Planthopper
- Breeding for and Genetics of Resistance
- Chemical control of the Brown Planthopper
- Methodology for Studying Varietal Resistance

In addition, papers were presented on the status of varietal resistance for brown planthopper control in India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Philippines, Solomon Islands, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Thailand.

The proceedings of the symposium will be published in the future.

Seedling reaction to bacterial blight

Nirmaljit Singh and Harnam Singh, Department of Plant Pathology, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab; S. S. Saini, Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, India

One hundred and ninety cultures of rice were tested against a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* during Jul-August 1976. The two youngest, fully expanded leaves of each 30-day-old

seedling were clipped at about 6 cm from the tip with scissors dipped in a bacterial suspension of 10⁷ cells/ml of 48-hour-old culture grown on potato sucrose peptone agar. The disease reaction was determined by measuring the lesion length (cm) from the point of inoculation of 20-25 leaves at 14 days after inoculation. Cross combinations, lesion lengths, and resistance ratings are shown in the table.

Lesion lengths and bacterial blight resistance ratings of several cross combinations tested in India.

Cross combination	Cultures tested (no.)	Av. lesion length (cm)	Rating ^a
Bas 370/Jaya	54	8.6	MS
Norin 18/Hyb 27	52	10.3	S
Mutants of Basmati 370	33	9.6	S
Bas 370/Hamsa	22	9.0	MS
Bas 370/IR127-80-1-10	5	11.2	S
IRS/Bas 370	4	9.3	S
Phulpattas 72/Mut 65	4	9.1	S
Bas 370/IR8	3	11.3	S
Hyb 27/Mut 65	2	9.8	S
Mut 52/Bas 370	1	8.4	MS
Bas 370/IR480-5	1	9.0	MS
UPR 71-12	1	3.2	MR
UPR 71-21	1	5.8	MR
UPR 70/30-4	1	5.4	MR
UPR 70/30-7	1	5.6	MR
UPR 70/30-14	1	7.4	MS
UPR 70/30-15	1	6.2	MS
UPR 70/30-25	1	3.2	MR
UPR 70/30-26	1	5.2	MR
UPR 70/30-39	1	4.4	MR
IR8	—	8.6	MS
Jaya	—	8.0	MS

^aMR = moderately resistant (lesion length 3.2-5.8 cm); M S = moderately susceptible (6.2-9.0 cm); S = susceptible (9.1-11.3 cm).